

INGLIZ TILINI O'QITISHDAGI TOPSHIRIQLAR TIPOLOGIYASI (3-4-SINF DARSLIKLARI MISOLIDA)

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Sergeli tumanidagi 300-ixtisoslashgan maktab ingliz tili o'qituvchisi
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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitishda foydalaniladigan 1-2-sinf darsliklarida grammatik topshiriqlar turli metodologik yondashuvlar va ta'lim usullariga asoslanishi yoritilgan. Shuningdek, darsliklar o'quvchilarga tilni o'rganishda yordam berish uchun turli mavzular, grammatika qoidalari, leksika, gapirish, tinglash, o'qish va yozish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradigan topshiriqlar va materiallar taqdim etilishi bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: boshlang'ich sinf, chet tili, grammatik bilim, darsliklar tahlili, "Teacher's book", "Student's book", "Workbook" darsliklar, topshiriqlar tipologiyasi, grammatik topshiriqlar.

O'quvchilarning faolligini oshirish uchun o'yinlar, jamoaviy ishlash, rol o'ynash kabi metodlar ko'p qo'llaniladi. Bu metodlar o'quvchilarni tilni o'rganish jarayoniga faollashtiradi. Darsliklarda yangi o'rganilgan mavzularni takrorlash uchun turli xil mashqlar (gaplar tuzish, dialoglar o'qish) beriladi. Bu metod o'quvchilarning bilimlarini mustahkamlashga yordam beradi. Audiovizual materiallar, video materiallar, interaktiv ilovalar darslarda foydalanish uchun kiritilgan. Bu o'quvchilarga tinglab tushunish va so'zlashuv ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda yordam beradi. Susannah Reed, Kay Bentley, Lesley Koustaff. Guess What! Student's Book 3. English language Grade 3 darsligida tinglash, o'qish va gapirishga oid topshiriqlar berilgan [5] (1-jadvalga qarang):

1-jadval.

3-sinf Ingliz tili darsligi topshiriqlari

T/r	Topshiriqlar	Unit 1	Unit 2	Unit 3	Unit 4	Unit 5	Unit 6	Unit 7	Unit 8
1.	Listen, point, and say / Listen and point	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2.	Listen, point, and repeat	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
3.	Listen and repeat. Then act / Listen and repeat	10	5	3	4	3	3	5	5
4.	Listen and say/say ...	4	1	1	3		2	2	2
5.	Listen and match	1	1						
6.	Listen again and say true or false	1		1	1			1	
7.	Listen and look. Then listen and repeat		1						

8.	Listen and choose			1		1	1		
9.	Listen and answer				1	1	1		
10.	Listen and find. Then answer the question					1			
11.	Describe and guess	2	1			1		1	
12.	Read and listen / then match	3	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
13.	Read again and answer the questions	1	1				1		
14.	Read and match	1	1						
15.	Read and say ...						1		1
16.	Match the	2			1			1	
17.	Make sentences about / Say true or false		1	1	1	1	1		1
18.	Make your own word puzzles for your friend		1		1		2		1
19.	Make sentences and guess			1					
20.	Ask and answer with a friend	6	2	2	1	3	3	2	1
21.	Ask questions and guess						1		1
22.	Sing the song	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
23.	Say the				1			1	
24.	Look and find		1						
25.	Look at Answer the questions		1			1		1	1
26.	Look at the song and find the differences in this picture							1	1
27.	Watch the video	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
28.	What can you see	1				1			

29.	What would you like ...	1							
30.	What type of ...	1					2		
31.	What can you ...?		1						
32.	What materials does your school recycle?		1						
33.	Which?			2					
34.	What time is it in your country?				1				
35.	Where would you like ...					1			
36.	Which sea animals do you like?								2
37.	Find the ... in the puzzles		1		1				2
38.	Play the game		1		1		1		1
39.	Now read and answer the questions			1	1				
40.	Choose a day from your schedule. Play a guessing game			1					

3-4-sinf darsliklarida o'quvchilarga grammatika (fe'l va otlarning oddiy shakllari), so'z boyligi (kundalik hayotda qo'llaniladigan iboralar va so'zlar) taqdim etiladi. Darsliklar o'quvchilarni boshqa madaniyatlar bilan tanishtirish, ingliz tilidagi oddiy matnlarni o'qish va yig'ish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan. 3-sinf Ingliz tili darsligi topshiriqlari diagramma ko'rinishida keltirildi (1-rasmga qarang):

1-rasm. Student's Book 3 darsligi topshiriqlari

Susannah Reed, Kay Bentley, Lesley Koustaff. Guess What! Student's Book 4. English language Grade 4 darsligida tinglash, o`qish va gapirishga oid topshiriqlar berilgan [6] (2-jadvalga qarang):

2-jadval.

4-sinf Ingliz tili darsligi topshiriqlari

T/r	Topshiriqlar	Unit 1	Unit 2	Unit 3	Unit 4	Unit 5	Unit 6	Unit 7	Unit 8
1.	Listen, point, and say / Listen and point	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2.	Listen, point, and repeat	4	1	1	1	1	1	2	1
3.	Listen and repeat. Then act / Listen and repeat	7	4	5	6	4	5	3	5
4.	Listen and say/say ...	1	2	1	2		2	1	2
5.	Listen and match	3	1	1	1	1	2		1
6.	Listen again and say true or false			1		1		1	
7.	Listen and look. Then listen and repeat / follow		1						

8.	Listen and choose	1		1		1		1	
9.	Listen and answer	1			1	1	1	1	1
10.	Listen and find. Then answer the question	1							
11.	Describe and guess	1		1	1	1	1	1	
12.	Read and listen / then match	3	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
13.	Read again and answer the questions/choose the words	2	1		2		1		1
14.	Read and match	1	1	1					
15.	Read and say ...				1		1		1
16.	Make sentences about / Say true or false	1	1		1				
17.	Make your own word puzzles for your friend		1		1		1		1
18.	Make sentences and guess // Make questions					2		1	
19.	Ask and answer with a friend	4	2	2	2	1		1	4
20.	Ask questions and guess						1	1	
21.	Sing the song								
22.	Say/tell the	1		1		1			
23.	Look and find/choose	1							
24.	Look at Answer the questions			1					1
25.	Look at the song and find the differences in this picture		1		1				
26.	Watch the video	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

27.	What ... can you see ...	2	2			1			1
28.	What are//kind of....?	2		1	2			3	1
29.	Which ta.....?							1	
30.	Where would you like/ Where are the big rivers in your country?					1			
31.	Find the ...		1		1				1
32.	Play the game		2		1		2	1	1
33.	Now read and answer the questions						1		
34.	Choose what you want to be. Then ask and answer		1						

4-sinf Ingliz tili darsligi topshiriqlari diagramma ko`rinishida keltirildi (2-rasmga qarang):

2-rasm. Student's Book 4 darsligi topshiriqlari

Xulosa qilib aytganda, darsliklarda o'quvchilarning bilimini baholash uchun kichik testlar, mashqlar va maxsus vazifalar mavjud. Bu o'quvchilarning til o'rganishdagi yutuqlarini va kamchiliklarini aniqlashga yordam beradi. O'quvchilarning qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish uchun

ularning o'zlashtirgan bilimlarini doimiy ravishda tahlil qilish va takrorlash kerak. Darsliklarda bunday imkoniyatlar ko'rsatilgan bo'lishi lozim. Darsliklar o'quvchilarga ingliz tilini samarali o'rgatishda asosiy vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Ular o'quvchilarning turli kommunikativ vaziyatlarda tilni qo'llay olishlariga yordam beradi.

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